

PEDAGOGICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article explains the best principles of innovative development of educational institutions and their management from the very first principle to the socio-economic principle of the developing country.

Key words: Educational development, Conceptual, Organizational and activity, Scientific-methodological level

The main part: The development of education serves to solve the problems of socio-economic development of the country and is one of the priorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In order to maintain its position in the domestic and world markets, our country must maintain a high position. The level of education provided in schools and universities. In solving this problem, it is important to ensure effective management of educational institutions. The economic conditions of the country lead universities to the commercialization of education and scientific activity and the ability to create and use the results of scientific and technical creativity. Scientific products produced in educational and higher education institutions should be innovative and competitive. The use of innovative mechanisms increases competitiveness and the quality of educational services. A modern higher education institution can promote innovative activities independently or in cooperation with other universities or commercial enterprises. projects from concept to implementation. The solution to the problem of improving the effectiveness of education requires the development of a management optimization strategy. Therefore, the modern activities of higher education should include the study of innovative activities. Modern trends and changes in the field of higher education are reflected in the transfer of universities from the classical model of education to the model of innovative education. In connection with these trends, the problem of innovative management is processes in the educational environment. By turning the typification of innovations into education, we can

determine the influencing factors on innovative activity and innovation management, these are: organizational, technological; motivational, informational, intellectual, technical. The need to develop an innovative environment, activation of innovative activity determines the relevance of research in the field of innovation management in higher educational institutions.

At the moment, serious changes are being made in the national education policy in our country. Due to this, the transition to a self-oriented pedagogic position. One of the tasks of the modern high school is to reveal the potential of all participants of the pedagogical process, to give an opportunity to show their creative abilities. Thus, the change of the role of education in society mainly led to innovative processes. About high-level innovation

Education, researchers distinguish three levels of innovation:

- conceptual
- Organizational activity
- Scientific and methodical

1. The conceptual level reflects the need to perform the following tasks:

- Methodological justification of previous general scientific ideas necessary and sufficient for its development
- The concept of restoration;
- Orientation to the pedagogical theory that gives an idea of the integrity of the educational process;
- The concept clearly reflects the specific work of the HEI.

2. The level of organization and activity implies the achievement of the following goals:

- Selection and appointment of teaching personnel, search and attraction of scientific consultants at the Higher Education Institution; specialists in conducting new courses and electives;
- Establishing a scientific and methodological council for planning, coordination and control of experimental work;
- Organization of creative groups of experimental teachers to develop and test new courses;
- Provision of material and technical conditions for conducting experimental work.

3. The scientific-methodical level implies the following:

- Development and testing of various options of educational plans, programs, ways and means of their achievement;
- Determining the level of knowledge and developing methods of obtaining knowledge;
- Highlight the efficiency criteria for the implementation of the educational concept of this Higher Education Institution;
- Determining an effective mechanism for the generalization and dissemination of best practices and innovations;
- Scientific provision of effective methods of teacher training and professional development.

Conclusion: Taking into account the process of innovation management in educational institutions, we can define innovative activity as a set of HEI processes: educational, scientific-innovative and strategic processes of human potential formation. Teachers of higher education organizations can be involved in these processes. Taking into account innovative activities, it is appropriate to emphasize the motivation and readiness of teachers for innovation. It should be taken into account that the effectiveness of innovative activity is ensured if teachers are motivated, if they are ready for innovation; able to eliminate the causes of resistance, that is, teachers are involved in innovation. This is ensured by the introduction of the author's technology of management of the innovation process in the department. The extrapolation of the components of the technology developed in the organization of HEI work ensures effective management of innovative processes in the specified educational organization.

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